

ADAPTING DESIGN THINKING APPROACH TO ENHANCE EFL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC WRITING PERFORMANCE AND CREATIVE THINKING SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays foreign language instructors have been implemented various pedagogical approaches in the classrooms, such as Design Thinking and Challenge-Based Learning etc, to enhance students' learning skills. Design thinking is a multi-step learning methodology that enhances creativity, collaboration, and problem-solving through practical projects. We aim to examine to assess the effectiveness of the Design Thinking process within the educational context to improve the academic writing performance and creative thinking skills of English as Foreign Language (EFL) students. This paper presents a structured pedagogical framework that incorporates the five stages of Design Thinking—Empathize, Define, Ideate, Prototype, and Test—into classroom instruction. The respondents of this qualitative study consist of both teachers and students from anonymous University in the English Language Program. The research data was collected through a six-consecutive week intervention involving 32 university students and 2 faculty members, and results were analyzed. The qualitative and quantitative mixed methods were applied, incorporating assessments of the learning process, classroom observations, categorization, focus interview, student reflections and teachers' perspectives. The findings indicate that students noted that Design Thinking models played a significant role in enhancing their creative engagement and active participation in the academic setting. Furthermore, they expressed that this approach improved their problem-solving abilities, helping them effectively address real-life challenges. Educators have observed improvements in students' academic writing performances, particularly in generating ideas and project outcomes in the DT process. Additionally, they highlighted a significant improvement in students' creativity through both collaborative and individual problem-solving tasks.

Keywords: EFL students, Design Thinking, application, academic writing outcome, students' creativity.

INTRODUCTION

Today's learners face rapidly changing educational landscapes shaped by continuous technological advancement. To meet their evolving needs, we believe in cultivating dynamic and engaging learning environments that inspire curiosity, encourage collaboration, and empower students. By doing so, we can significantly enrich their educational journeys and help them realize their full potential. We would like to share our insights and experiences regarding the application of the Design Thinking approach to teaching activities that is based on practical results.

Design thinking is a multi-step learning methodology that enhances creativity, collaboration, and problem-solving through practical projects. Design thinking can be defined as a human-centered approach to problem solving that is built on empathy, collaboration, and teamwork. The concept of design thinking (DT) has various interpretations across fields but primarily focuses on innovation and adaptability. It allows educators to tackle issues from multiple perspectives, offering diverse solutions. Recently, DT has gained attention as a valuable educational paradigm, combining cross-disciplinary knowledge and skills. This approach benefits both educators and students in addressing complex challenges. It provides valuable insights for learners and educators, highlighting that innovation can take many forms, including services, products, and changes in behavior. Despite its recent prominence in many sectors, Design Thinking (DT) dates back to the 1960s, when it was used in architecture and engineering. Horst Rittel coined the phrase "wicked problem" in the mid-1960s to describe multiple complicated challenges, as well as the approaches required to address them. In his

1987 book "Design Thinking", Peter Rowe professor of Harvard University of Design formally introduced the idea of design thinking (Zhang, 2023). Institutions like the Stanford Design School and well-known design businesses like IDEO popularized DT, bringing it into the educational mainstream (Buchanan, 1992). DT is also employed in Montessori schools due to its hands-on nature, aligning with Maria Montessori's methods and sharing traits with 20th-century educational theories like those of Dewey and Kolb (Beták, 2022). DT can be extensively used for academic and administrative problems in the field of English language education and can be useful in the following areas: developing an instructional method, improving course material, deciding on a teaching strategy to achieve subject-specific learning goals, facilitating student support through mentoring and coaching, professional development, in-service training, and managing change and rebuilding organizational culture (Panke, 2019).

The DT frame consists of five phases such as: Empathize, Define, Ideate, Prototype, and Test. Integrating the design thinking approach into curriculum development can enhance a school culture that prioritizes the needs of students and teachers. In English language classrooms, Design Thinking (DT) encourages collaboration and fosters critical thinking and problem-solving skills (Adams et al., 2015). It helps students develop empathy and address real-world challenges flexibly.

DT can also improve testing and evaluation by engaging students in assessment development, increasing their understanding of language goals and promoting creative thinking. For educators, DT provides strategies for addressing challenges in curriculum development and student motivation, strengthening relationships,

and enhancing support programs. In management and leadership, DT offers a framework for tackling complex school improvement issues by promoting inclusive decision-making and collaboration, ultimately strengthening the school system and promoting quality assurance (Ustunluoglu, 2024).

Paraphrasing is an essential skill in academic writing, allowing students to convey ideas in their own words while maintaining the original meaning. However, many EFL students find paraphrasing challenging due to limited vocabulary, grammatical constraints, and difficulties in restructuring sentences effectively. Traditional approaches to teaching paraphrasing often focus on rote memorization and mechanical exercises rather than fostering deep understanding and creative problem-solving. This study proposes an alternative instructional strategy by integrating the Design Thinking approach into EFL pedagogy to improve students' paraphrasing skills.

Literature review

Numerous studies have investigated the incorporation of Design Thinking within English Language Teaching (ELT) with an emphasis on empowering learners. For example, research by Johnson and Millard analyzed the effects of Design Thinking concepts in an ELT setting. They discovered that by integrating empathy and proactive problem-solving, students not only advanced their language abilities but also showed increased self-confidence and self-efficacy in their communication in English. The research illustrated that Design Thinking promotes a more learner-centered educational environment, where students actively confront language challenges and collaboratively seek solutions. A study by Smith and Brown (2020) examined the ideation phase of Design Thinking in English Language Teaching (ELT). They found that creative language use through multimedia projects and collaborative storytelling improved language acquisition and student motivation. By allowing students to explore language creatively, they became more engaged and developed a stronger connection to the language. This research highlights the potential of Design Thinking in fostering creativity and critical thinking skills while enhancing language proficiency, ultimately creating more engaging learning experiences in ELT (Sotlikova, 2023). Mārīte Opincāne (2023) and Karīne Laganovska examined the effectiveness of the Design Thinking approach in teaching foreign languages to Bachelor law students learning legal English and Bachelor IT students studying German. Their study found that this approach helps learners tackle real-life problems and is particularly beneficial for those with a higher proficiency in foreign languages. Lightbown and Spada noted that effective thinking skills emerge when students engage in classroom discussions, while R. Jones highlighted that language fosters creativity due to its rule-based, ambiguous, and socially interactive nature. According to Mujiono (2024) modern pedagogies emphasize moving from rigid, top-down methods to flexible, learner-centric approaches, where students become active collaborators for a more meaningful learning experience. In EFL education, there's a shift toward highlighting linguistic proficiency alongside cultural and contextual

understanding to create globally aware individuals capable of navigating international dialogues. The integration of Design Thinking with EFL education offers a promising path for pedagogical innovation. By focusing on the learner's journey and individual needs, this approach can enhance language instruction while fostering a deep understanding of cultural contexts, empathy, and global collaboration. Marite (2023) highlighted that trend in this field change over time; for instance, the focus in the 1980s was on business letters, whereas now e-communication is key. The emphasis has shifted to language function over specific language items. The main benefits of an efficient foreign language syllabus for specific purposes are speed, efficiency, and effectiveness in learning. Sotlikova (2023) described Design Thinking as a student-centered problem-solving framework that prioritizes learners. It encourages students to empathize with users, define problems, brainstorm creative solutions, prototype their ideas, and test them in real-world contexts. Gabriela emphasizes that constructive learning training is essential for students to effectively use metacognitive skills. Moreover, a design thinking strategy helps EFL university students enhance collaboration, efficacy, and problem-solving abilities (Gabriela Almache-Grande, 2024).

Theoretical Framework of the study

According to Chen design, thinking effectively integrates constructivism into teaching and learning. Constructivism enables students to create their own understanding through knowledge construction. However, its implementation can be complex without a clear method; hence, design thinking serves as an effective approach. It fosters essential skills for constructive learning, such as exploration, receptiveness, creativity, and metacognition. Additionally, design thinking emphasizes social learning, which Vygotsky (1978) identified as crucial for cognitive development through collaborative interaction (Bezabih Mitiku, 2024).

A ready-made guide by IDEO was used to enhance students' grasp of design thinking. This guide begins with "empathy," exploring students' ability to connect with various user needs. It progresses to "problem definition," emphasizing the clear identification of challenges. In the "ideation" phase, the emphasis lies on innovative thought processes, transitioning to the "prototyping" stage where ideas evolve into tangible models. The suitability of these prototypes for real-world applications is subsequently assessed. During the "implementation" phase, the efficacy of students' application of theoretical knowledge is gauged, concluding with a "reflection" on their methodologies and outcomes.

2. Findings

The participants of this study consists of both teachers and students from anonymous University in the English Language Program. Consequently, through a blend of qualitative and quantitative methods, we intended to assess the effectiveness of the Design Thinking process within the educational context. The study was carried out in an engaging EFL (English as a Foreign Language) classroom, involving 32 university students at the intermediate level. The participants were

divided into two distinct groups, A and B, fostering a collaborative learning environment. A mixed-methods approach was used, including assessments of the learning process, classroom observations, and students' and teachers' reflections. The intervention lasted for six

weeks and incorporated activities that aligned with the five stages of Design Thinking.

For a comprehensive understanding of the design thinking mindset and its specific indicators, see Table 1. Design thinking process for Academic Writing (Kang, 2021).

Table 1

Design thinking approach tasks and instructions

N #	Task	Phases	Indicators	Description	Instructions
1	Writing a term paper	Empathize	Identify user needs and challenges. Clarify reader needs, writing goals, and research questions.	Understanding the Problem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Write an academic paper on improving academic writing skills under the topic of "Paraphrasing and use standard formatting. Work in pairs or groups to analyze examples of poorly paraphrased sentences (e.g., overly similar wording, incorrect meaning, or structure). Reflect on personal struggles with paraphrasing (e.g., difficulty finding synonyms, changing sentence structure).
2		Define:	Identify the problem and formulate a research question.	Clarifying the learning Challenge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As a team, create a problem statement: Example: "How might we develop strategies to paraphrase effectively while maintaining meaning and clarity?" List common issues in paraphrasing (e.g., lack of vocabulary, difficulty with sentence restructuring).
3		Ideation	Propose numerous solutions to address the issue. Formulate discussions, theories or concepts for research studies.	Generating Solutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Brainstorm different paraphrasing strategies Find creative solutions like paraphrasing a game or creating a step-by-step guide.
4		Prototype	Develop a physical or digital representation of the solution. Construct a framework or initial draft for a term paper.	Prototyping & Language Learning in Action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct the simple interviews or surveys Gather data through observation, surveys and interviews. Students apply different strategies to paraphrase short passages. They compare their paraphrases with peers and provide feedback. Create a Paraphrasing Sheet with tips and strategies.
5		Testing	Get feedback on the prototype and make necessary improvements. Revise based on input from teachers or peers.	Refining and evaluating	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyze data and write a proposal. Content Includes: Original texts + their paraphrased versions; Peer and teacher feedback. Self-reflections on improvement. Reflect on what strategies worked best and what needs improvement. Revise their paraphrases based on feedback and discuss lessons learned.

In the first step of Empathize stage: Instructors consider that students are facing challenges with academic writing skills. In the Defining stage: Two groups of the students were given paper assignments under the topic of "Improving academic writing skills in terms of Paraphrasing". Students then analyzed common paraphrasing difficulties and shared their challenges. The teams collaboratively identified key problems such as

limited use of synonyms and accurate sentence structures are main writing challenges. In the Ideate stage: The students were divided into teams of four and engaged in a Design Thinking process to enhance their paraphrasing skills. During the Ideation phase, they brainstormed creative paraphrasing strategies, incorporating visual aids, storytelling techniques, and collaborative exercises. In the Prototype stage, students practiced paraphrasing using various methods and received

peer feedback. This continued into the Test stage, where they further experimented with different writing techniques and revised their work based on the feedback received. Throughout the process, students assumed dual roles as both DT designers and end-users, tackling challenges designed to strengthen their academic writing and foster creative thinking. During the

phase, they shared their discoveries with one another through oral presentations. They learned from each other by communicating. Together, they tried different approaches to solve their challenges. This approach aims to develop students' language skills through activities like brainstorming, collaboration, and rewriting.

Figure 1 Students' opinions regarding the effectiveness of the DT process

The data presents findings from students' questionnaire responses and their evaluations of the design thinking process related to their academic writing assignment. The findings from the initial question reveal that a large percentage, 78.6%, stated that participating in the design thinking process inspired them to undertake research papers. This indicates that design thinking models played a significant role in enhancing their creative engagement and active participation within the academic environment. 20% of the students indicated "Neutral," suggesting they encounter challenges and difficulties completing the project. In response to the second question, 69% of the students expressed that it enhanced their problem-solving abilities, which can be understood as it assisting students in effectively addressing real-life challenges. Thirty percent of the participants responded neutrally, indicating that they do not feel a significant influence on the project they completed. Therefore, teachers should consider various methods to guide them in developing their problem-solving skills. In addressing the third question, an impressive 98.4% of students expressed agreement that the DT project enhanced their teamwork skills. This

improvement is indicative of a positive impact on communicative creativity and fosters collaboration among participants. For the fourth question, 50% of the respondents answered "Neutral" regarding whether it "allowed them to improve their creative and critical thinking skills." This response may indicate a balanced perspective, suggesting that the respondents see both sides of the argument equally. It is possible they did not experience significant changes in their writing skills. Therefore, conducting follow-up interviews could be beneficial to understand their reasoning better. On the contrary, 48.3% of the students agreed that it improved their creative and critical thinking skills, indicating that it helps them improve their higher-order skills.

In the final question, 52% of the respondents indicated a "Neutral" stance regarding whether the Design Thinking (DT) process helped improve their academic writing skills. This suggests that many respondents may lack sufficient knowledge or experience with the DT process. Since it was their first experience using this approach for learning, they may have encountered difficulties in understanding the process. On the other hand, 48% of the students agreed that the DT approach helped them enhance their academic writing skills.

Figure 2 Comparison of term paper outcomes of the A& B groups (by percentage)

Figure 2 displays the overall performance of two groups on the academic writing assignment (term paper), including criteria that teachers such as the use of the DT process, creativity, attention to detail, productivity, quality of the academic paper and oral presentation skills. We evaluate the project outcomes using a ready-made rubric, which categorizes scores as follows: Advanced (90-100%), Proficient (80-89%), Developing (70-79%), and Needs Improvement (60-69%).

The outcomes of the project were evaluated at the end of the design thinking process. Students are learning to utilize the design thinking (DT) process for their projects. This assessment provides a general overview of the design thinking stages, as well as students' understanding and experience with the approach. Group A performed better, achieving an 86% success rate, compared to Group B, which scored 80%. The goal of the first criteria is evaluating the unique solutions to the problem and determining whether they fulfill their

goals. It assesses creativity and originality by examining various perspectives and solutions for the project's outcomes. Group "A" achieved a score of 90%.

The third criterion evaluates students' problem-solving skills in academic writing projects. Group A scores 88%, while Group B scores 77%. The fourth criterion assesses effective use of project time to enhance academic writing. Collaborate with peers and instructors as needed to make project time more efficient. Both groups made significant efforts to achieve the goals, earning proficient scores. The fifth criterion assesses the quality of the academic assignment, including the plagiarism report and adherence to the university's format guidelines. Both groups show positive outcomes.

Our final criteria involved evaluating their public speaking skills to present their project outcomes to classmates and share ideas with peers.

The second half of the survey, which included five questions, the two educators who implemented the Design Thinking approach in their teaching were interviewed. Interview questions are as shown in Table 3.

Table 3

Perspectives of instructors on the effectiveness of Design Thinking in academic writing assignments

Criteria	Improvement scale	Frequency level
1. Have you observed an improvement in your students' writing skills as a result of using the Design Thinking approach?	Significant improvement Moderate improvement No improvement	2/2 0 0
2. Have you noticed any improvement in students' ability to develop ideas after being involved in creating and problem-solving activities?	Significant improvement Moderate improvement No improvement	2/2 0 0
3. Have you noticed that students become more proficient in writing assignments after going through feedback loops to revise and enhance their drafts?	Significant improvement Moderate improvement No improvement	0 2/2 0
4. Have you observed that problem-solving activities, whether done in groups or individually, have enhanced students' creativity?	Significant improvement Moderate improvement No improvement	2/2 0 0
5. Have you noticed that students show increased confidence in public speaking after participating in the drafting or generation of ideas?	Significant improvement Moderate improvement No improvement	2/2 0 0

(Gabriela Almache-Granda, 2024)

The educators have supported the idea that students' academic writing performance have improved. They observed a significant improvement in students' writing abilities and idea generation, along with a moderate enhancement in their proficiency with writing assignments, following their engagement in feedback loops to revise and refine their drafts. Additionally, they reported that students have demonstrated a notable increase in creativity skills through problem-solving

tasks, both collaboratively and individually. Likewise, they concurred that a significant improvement was observed in students' public speaking abilities following their involvement in teamwork activities.

What are the primary challenges faced by educators and the strategies they use to address them when implementing Design Thinking?

The findings from this section are displayed in Table 4.

Table 4

Summary statistics regarding the effects of challenges on Design Thinking

Challenges	Least Influence (minimum)	Most Influence (maximum)	Total
Number of students	1		1
Time		1	1
Resources	1		1
Student comprehension		1	1
Low student motivation		1	1
Traditional student mindset		1	1
Student Collaboration and Teamwork Dynamics		1	1
Adapting Design Thinking to Different learning styles	1		1
Access to Technology and Tools	1		1
Integration of Design Thinking with Existing Curriculum		1	1
	4	6	

Table 4 illustrates the challenges that have had the greatest and the least influence on educators' experiences with implementing Design Thinking. Among the highest impact challenges identified are time management, student comprehension, low student motivation, traditional student mindsets, collaboration and teamwork dynamics, the integration of design thinking into the existing curriculum, and the number of students in a class. These results indicate that incorporating design thinking into the current curriculum is a significant concern, along with the motivation levels of students. The transition from a traditional mindset to a more active learning approach poses a challenge as well; it was rated among the highest challenges, with variation in

significance depending on the educators' perspectives. Additionally, class size is a concern because, in scenarios with excessive numbers of students, it becomes difficult to engage learners effectively. Conversely, the challenges with the lowest impact include the selection of resources for the design thinking process, which is not viewed as a major concern in comparison to other aspects. Similarly, adapting design thinking to different learning styles, as well as access to technology and tools, are not considered significant issues.

Ensuring the reliability of the research instruments methods of both quantitative and qualitative analysis are applied. We use bar chart data from A&B groups' outcome of the writing performance.

Table 5

Hypothesis Test Summary

Hypothesis Test Summary				
	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distribution of result is the same across categories of group.	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.132 ¹	Retain the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.

¹Exact significance is displayed for this test.

When testing whether the exam scores of students in Groups A and B are similarly distributed, the significance value was found to be $P(\text{sig}) = 0.132$, which is

greater than 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that there is no statistically significant difference between the exam scores of students in Groups A and B, meaning their scores are similar.

Table 6

Statistical analysis result

Correlations				
			result	teacher
Spearman's rho	result	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.774**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.003
		N	12	12
teacher	teacher	Correlation Coefficient	.774**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.
		N	12	12

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

An analysis of the relationship between students' exam scores and the teacher's evaluations in Groups A and B revealed a Spearman's correlation coefficient of 0.774, indicating a strong positive correlation between the two variables. The significance value was $p = 0.003$, which is below the conventional threshold of 0.05, suggesting that the correlation is statistically significant. These findings imply that the two forms of assessment are closely aligned, providing a reliable and valid measure of student performance.

3. Results and Discussion

The implementation of the design thinking process is essential for enhancing collaborative skills among learners. This aligns with the findings of Mārīte Opincāne and Karīne Laganovska (2023), who stated that the design thinking approach is effective because it encourages learners to solve real-life problems, fostering collaboration and active engagement as they discuss both simulated professional scenarios and real-world issues. According to Sotlikova (2023), the design thinking approach promotes teamwork and collaboration, as well as the development of creative and critical thinking skills. In this approach, students analyze cases, identify issues, propose solutions, and defend their recommendations. It encourages students to work together to tackle real-world problems. Additionally, this aligns with the findings of Taghreed Alrehaili and Sajjadllah Alhawsawi (2020), who state that design thinking-based writing instruction enhances students' writing

skills in areas such as organization, development, cohesion, structure, vocabulary, and mechanics, while also increasing their active participation and overall satisfaction.

4. Conclusion

The results of this study highlight the effectiveness of the Design Thinking approach in enhancing the academic writing outcome of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners, while also improving their creative and collaborative abilities. This research demonstrates that Design Thinking is an effective instructional strategy for developing academic skills in EFL classrooms. Students noted that Design Thinking models played a significant role in enhancing their creative engagement and active participation in the academic environment. Furthermore, they expressed that this approach improved their problem-solving abilities, helping them effectively address real-life challenges. By fostering creativity, collaboration, and iterative learning, students gain a deeper understanding of techniques and become more confident in their writing. Educators have observed improvements in students' academic writing skills, particularly in generating ideas and proficiency with assignments after participating in feedback loops. They also noted a significant rise in students' creativity through both collaborative and individual problem-solving tasks. Future research could explore the application of this approach to other academic

writing challenges, such as summarization and argumentation.

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